

Terpenoids and Related Compounds: Part II'. Neutral Constituents of the Leaves and Stem-Bark of *Ervatamia wallichiana* Steub.

Sunil K. Talapatra, Subrata Sen Gupta and Mrs. Bani Talapatra (née Ghoshary)

A pentacyclic triterpenoid of rare occurrence, characterised as bauerenol acetate by NMR and mass spectral analyses and by formation of its derivatives, has been isolated in good yield (0.03% in leaves and 0.04% in bark) from the neutral fractions of the petroleum extracts of the leaves and stem-bark of *Ervatamia wallichiana* Steub. (Fam. Apocynaceae). The leaves also furnished β -sitosterol and a saturated straight-chain hydrocarbon, *n*-hentriacontane associated with trace amounts of its second higher and lower homologues, *n*-tritriacontane and *n*-nonacosane respectively.

During the last few years a number of plants of the genus *Ervatamia* (Fam. Apocynaceae) and of the closely related genus *Tabernaemontana* have been investigated and have been found to produce indole alkaloids mainly of iboga type¹⁻³.

The study of the leaves and bark of *Ervatamia wallichiana* Steub. which still remains uninvestigated chemically, has been undertaken. The alkaloidal constituents of the same are being published elsewhere⁴.

The neutral fraction from the petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) extracts of the leaves and bark upon repeated chromatography over neutral alumina (Brockmann Grade I) yielded three crystalline solids. The major constituent has been found to be a triterpenoid as evidenced from its pink colouration with Liebermann-Burchardt reagent. It gives a well-defined single spot in TLC ($R_f=0.80$, using silica gel as absorbent and benzene as developer). The triterpene compound crystallises from petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) in fine glistening flakes, m.p. 284-85°, [α]_D²⁵ -3°(CHCl₃). It analysed for C₅₄H₉₀O₈, supported by its molecular ion peak at *m/e* 468. The compound contains an acetoxy group (peaks at 5.81 and 8.01 μ in the IR and a 3 proton singlet at 2.04 δ in the NMR spectra), a *gem* dimethyl group (an ill-defined multiplet around 7.29 μ , a 6-proton singlet at 0.92 δ) and probably six more methyl groups (singlets at 0.75, 0.82, 0.97 and 1.02 δ , total intensity about 18 protons) and a trisubstituted double bond (an ill-defined 1-proton triplet around 5.45 δ for vinylic proton). The chloroform solution of the triterpene acetate produces yellow colour with tetranitromethane showing the presence of unsaturation. Hydrolysis of the acetate furnishes an alcohol, C₅₀H₇₈O, m.p. 202-03°, [α]_D²⁵ -25°(CHCl₃) which shows a new peak at 2.9 μ

1. Part I. Cava, Talapatra, Weisbach, Raffauf, Douglas and Beal, *Lloydia*, 1962, 25, 222.
2. Gorman, Neuss, Cone and Deyrup, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 1142.
3. Cava, Mowdood and Beal, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1964, 2064.
4. Govindachari, Joshi, Sakseena, Sathe and Viswanathan, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 3873; *Chem. Comm.*, 1966, 97.
5. Kupchan, Cassidy and Telang, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 1251.
6. Talapatra, Sen Gupta, Bhattacharya and Talapatra, paper in preparation.

for -OH instead of the peaks at 5.82 and 8.01 μ for acetoxy group present in the parent compound. The m.p.s, molecular formulae and rotations of the above two compounds correspond to those recorded in the literature for bauerenol acetate^{7,8} (Ia) and bauerenol^{7,8} (Ib), triterpenoid compounds of rare occurrence.

Ia, R=CO.CH₃

Ib, R=H

Ic, R=COC₆H₅

Our NMR data also agree well with the structure of bauerenol acetate (Ia). This was further confirmed by the preparation of bauerenol benzoate (Ic), crystallised from chloroform-acetone mixture in needles, m.p. 249-50°C, [α]_D²⁰ +14° (CHCl₃), the physical constants being in good accord with those reported in the literature^{7,8}. The identity of our sample was finally established by melting point determination in admixture and IR comparison with an authentic sample of bauerenol acetate.

The mass fragmentation patterns of our sample and its hydrolysed products have been found to be similar to that observed⁹ in case of triterpenes of bauereus series having methyl groups at positions 13 and 14 which influence the characteristic breakdown pattern.

Due to enhanced strain imposed by C₁₃ methyl group most of the fragmentation occurs in the environment of C₇/D ring juncture. Bauerenol shows an intense peak (base peak) at m/e 247 (M-170) in its mass spectrum. The genesis of the characteristic base peak may be rationalised as shown in the following scheme.

It may be assumed that migration of the double bond in bauerenol takes place to give isobauerenol (II)⁹ which then suffers a retro-Diels-Alder decomposition of ring C followed by cleavage of the allylically activated 15-16 bond giving rise to fragment (m/e 247). Alternatively, fission of the 13-14 bond accompanied by a rearrangement of the C₇ hydrogen yields the same intermediate (III).

This is the second isolation of bauerenol acetate from nature, the first being from another spocynaceous plant *Kopsia longiflora*¹⁰. The free alcohol bauerenol was first reported from *Acronychia baueri*⁷. Later it was also reported from *Gelonium multiflorum*⁸ (Fam. Euphorbiaceae).

7. Lahey and Leeding, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 342.

8. Sen Gupta and Khastgir, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 123.

9. Budzikiewicz, Wilson and Djerassi, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3688.

10. Crow and Michael, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1955, 8, 129.

The other two neutral constituents were obtained from the petroleum extract of leaves. The identity of one of them having molecular formula $C_{30}H_{50}O$, m.p. 139° , $[\alpha]_D^{25}$

-36° ($CHCl_3$) with β -sitosterol¹¹ has been established from mixed m.p. determination and IR spectral comparison with an authentic sample as well as by preparing its acetate, m.p. 135° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} -39^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$).

The third neutral constituent crystallising from ethyl acetate or acetone in fine flakes, m.p. $67-70^\circ$, is free from any functional group (no absorption in hydroxyl, carbonyl or ether region in the IR spectrum). Negative tetranitromethane test and absence of any selected or end absorption in the UV region suggest that it is a saturated hydrocarbon. The above data in conjunction with its mass number ($M^+ = 438$) indicate its identity with a saturated straight chain hydrocarbon, n -hentriacontane¹², $C_{31}H_{64}$, supported by its elemental analyses. The mass spectrum also shows that the compound is associated with trace amounts of its second higher and lower homologues, n -tritriacontane, $C_{33}H_{68}$ ($M^+ = 466$) and n -nonacosane, $C_{29}H_{60}$ ($M^+ = 410$) respectively. Direct comparison could not be made due to the unavailability of a sample of n -hentriacontane.

11. Heilbron, Bunbury, Cook and Jones, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Vol. 4, Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953, p. 361.

12. Ref. 11, Vol. 2, p. 636.

EXPERIMENTAL

Investigation on Leaves of Ervatamia wallichiana Steub.—Dried and powdered leaves (1.5 kg) of *Ervatamia wallichiana* Steub. was extracted successively with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) (A), chloroform (B) and ethanol (C). The petroleum ether extract (A) was made free from the basic compounds⁶ by extracting with 2*N* hydrochloric acid. The base-free non-aqueous layer which was found to be free from acidic components was washed with saturated sodium chloride solution, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated. The resulting residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina (150 g) (Brockmann Grade I) and eluted with petroleum (b.p. 40-60°), benzene, benzene-ether (1:1) and ether respectively.

Isolation of n-Hentriacontane.—Petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) eluted fractions yielding only one spot in TLC were mixed together and concentrated to yield a white residue (105 mg). It was recrystallised from ethyl acetate in fine flakes, m.p. 67-70°. The compound was soluble in petroleum (b.p. 40-60° and b.p. 60-80°) but sparingly soluble in ethyl acetate, ether and ethanol. It showed negative test with tetranitromethane and no selected or end absorption in the UV region. These physical properties along with its molecular ion peak ($M^+ = 438$) are in good agreement with *n*-hentriacontane having molecular formula $C_{31}H_{64}$. (Found in a dry sample: C, 85.12; H, 14.62. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{64}$: C, 85.23; H, 14.77%).

Isolation of Bauerenol Acetate (Ia). The total benzene eluate fractions (giving a different spot of lower R_f in TLC) upon concentration furnished impure bauerenol acetate, m.p. 270-74°. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) to yield fine glistening flakes of pure bauerenol acetate (0.1 g), m.p. 283-84°, [α]_D²⁵ -3° (C, 0.95 in $CHCl_3$). The compound gave pink colouration with Liebermann Burchardt reagent (characteristic for triterpene). Homogeneity of the triterpene acetate was established by thin layer chromatography over silica-gel slide, a single spot ($R_f = 0.80$) has been obtained using benzene as developer. (Found: C, 81.64; H, 11.05. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.18%).

Bauerenol (Ib)—Bauerenol acetate (Ia) (0.08 g) was refluxed with 5% alcoholic potassium hydroxide (8 ml) for 2 hr. Removal of the solvent was accompanied by gradual addition of hot water when shining crystals were thrown out of the solution. The crystals were filtered and recrystallised from methanol-acetone mixture in fine glistening needles, m.p. 202-203°, [α]_D²⁵ -25° (c, 0.955 in chloroform). (Found: C, 84.75; H, 11.51. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.5; H, 11.7%).

Bauerenol benzoate (Ic).—Bauerenol (0.1 g) was benzoylated at room temperature by shaking with benzoyl chloride (1.0 ml) and pyridine (2.0 ml). The solution assumed faint pink colour and shining crystals began to separate from the reaction mixture within a few minutes. The reaction was found to be complete within $\frac{1}{4}$ hr. (monitored by TLC experiments). Pouring of the reaction mixture in ice-water containing few drops of hydrochloric acid was followed by thorough extraction with ether. Evaporation of the ether extract after washing with saturated sodium chloride solution and drying, gave impure bauerenol benzoate which was purified by several crystallisations from chloroform-acetone mixture and obtained as needles, (yield 0.08 g.), m.p. 249-50°, [α]_D²⁵ +14° (C, 0.85 in $CHCl_3$).

β -Sitosterol.—The benzene: ether (1:1) eluate after evaporation gave a solid, melting at 132-37°. It was purified by several crystallisations from methanol and had m.p. 138-39°, [α]_D²⁵ -36° (c, 0.741 in $CHCl_3$). The compound gave positive Liebermann-Burchardt colour test for sterol and tetranitromethane test for unsaturation. Mixed melting point

of this compound with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol was found to be undecomposed. (Found: C, 84.15; H, 12.01. Calc. for $C_{27}H_{46}O$: C, 84.07; H, 12.08%).

β -Sitosterol Acetate. A solution of β -sitosterol (0.2 g) dissolved in freshly distilled acetic anhydride (2 ml) was heated on a water bath with pyridine (0.4 ml) for 3 hr. Excess solvent was driven off in vacuum, the residue left was dissolved in a few ml of ethanol and poured in ice-cold water when a white precipitate of the acetate separated out. This was filtered, washed with water, dried and dissolved in ethanol. The alcoholic solution was boiled with a small amount of charcoal, hot filtered and concentrated when colourless shining plates of the acetyl derivative (yield 0.18 g) separated out. It was further purified by several crystallisations from methanol. The pure compound melted at 134-35°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -39° (c, 0.751 in $CHCl_3$).

The chloroform extract (B) was processed in the same way, the alkaloidal constituents are reported elsewhere⁶. The neutral fraction did not furnish any pure or crystalline solid even after repeated chromatography.

The alcoholic extract gave small residue which did not furnish any pure compound.

Investigation on Stem-bark.—Dried and powdered stem-bark (0.8 kg) of *Ervatamia wallichiana* Steub. was extracted successively with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform and ethanol. The petroleum extract on concentration deposited an amorphous solid (2 g), which upon chromatography over alumina (50 g) furnished a further quantity of baurenol acetate (0.9 g).

The authors are indebted to Professor (Mrs.) A. Chatterjee, University College of Science for her kind interest and encouragement in the work and for an authentic sample of β -sitosterol, to Dr. B. Des, Gif-Sur Yvette, Paris for mass spectral analyses and to Dr. M. Bahman for NMR spectrum. Thanks are due to Dr. P. Sen Gupta, Kalyani University for an authentic sample of baurenol acetate, to Dr. S. C. Pakrashi, Indian Institute of Biochemistry and Experimental Medicine, Calcutta for IR spectra, to Dr. T. K. Bose, Superintendent, Royal Horticultural Society, Calcutta for the generous supply of plant materials and to C.S.I.R. and U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.